

Acknowledgement

The authors express their sincere thanks to Dr. N.A. Ramaiah, Director of the Institute for his kind interest in this investigation.

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Chemical Constituents of *Wrightia coccinea* Sims.

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Manuscript received 8 January 1979, accepted 27 April 1979

WRIGHTIA coccinea (Fam. Apocynaceae) on which no systematic chemical investigation was made earlier, is a native of the high altitude Himalayan region. We have been attracted to this plant for the well known medicinal properties of the *Wrightia* species¹. In this communication we report the characterisation of two triterpenes and β -sitosterol along with an unidentified neutral compound isolated from this plant.

Air-dried powdered whole plant (1 kg) was successively extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°), chloroform and methanol. The petrol extract on concentration and cooling deposited a solid which on purification by chromatography over silica gel (60-100 mesh) followed by crystallisation from a mixture of methanol and chloroform gave a homogeneous compound (yield 0.5%), C₃₂H₅₂O₂ (M⁺468), m.p. 225°, [α]_D+77° (CHCl₃). It gave a positive Liebermann-Burchard reaction for a triterpene, and was finally identified with α -O-acetyl- α -amyrin by usual comparison (m.m.p., co-TLC and superimposable IR spectra) with an authentic sample as well as by its conversion to α -amyrin by alkaline hydrolysis.

The mother liquor of the above petrol extract on similar chromatographic resolution afforded β -sitosterol, m.p. 137-38° (acetate, m. p. 127-28°) characterised by comparison with an authentic sample.

The chloroform extract was chromatographed over silica gel and on elution with petrol-ethyl acetate (5:1) afforded a white solid in extremely poor yield (0.0002%), crystallised from methanol to give a compound, C₃₀H₅₀O₂ (M⁺442), m.p. 190-91°, [α]_D+34.5° (CHCl₃). It does not respond to Liebermann-Burchard reaction for a triterpene or a sterol. Its IR spectrum shows intense absorption at 3320 cm⁻¹ for hydroxyl function(s). The signals in the 80 MHz PMR spectrum of the compound in CDCl₃ at δ_{ppm} 5.50, 1H, br, signal ($\text{>C=CH-CH}_2\text{-}$); 3.2, 1H, br, signal (-CH-OH); 1.24, 9H, s; 0.90, 6H, s; 0.82, 6H,

s and 0.74, 3H, s (all for -C-CH_3), however, suggest

a triterpenoid nature of the compound having a trisubstituted double bond, a secondary alcohol and presumably a tertiary hydroxyl function. The MS of the compound showing significant peaks at m/e (relative intensity) 442 (M⁺, 9), 425 (18), 424 (53), 409 (39), 302 (39), 255 (20), 203 (51), 187 (26), 175 (37), 173 (23), 163 (20), 161 (33), 159 (20), 149 (29), 147 (46), 145 (21), 135 (46), 134 (23), 133 (39), 123 (27), 121 (60), 119 (40), 109 (86), 107 (64), 105 (40), 95 (86), 93 (56), 91 (30), 81 (69), 79 (34), 71 (22), 69 (70), 67 (38), 55 (83) and 43 (100) provides tangential evidence in support of the above contention. But the fragmentation pattern while showing some characteristic features² of the multiflorene, arborene, Δ^{10} -friedalene and Δ^{12} -lupene group of triterpenoids, does not fully correspond to any one of the above series of compounds. Further work on this compound is being delayed due to inadequate supply of the plant material.

Further elution of the column with petrol-ethyl acetate (4:1) afforded a triterpene acid (crystallised from aqueous ethanol, yield 0.001%). C₃₀H₄₈O₃, m.p. 290-1° [Methyl ester, 170°, [α]_D+58° (CHCl₃); methyl ester acetate, m.p. 245°], identified (m.m.p., co-TLC and IR) in all respects with an authentic sample of ursolic acid. The methanol extract did not give any characterisable compound. It is interesting to note that while *Wrightia* species are well known for elaborating steroidal bases, *W. coccinea* shows total absence of any alkaloid.

Acknowledgement

We thank Dr. D. A. Evans, University of Southampton, U.K. for the MS and Professor A. K. Barua, Bose Institute, Calcutta-700009 for an authentic sample of α -amyrin acetate.

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